

Supplementary Materials

Here is a list summarizing our predictors for random forests:

- *LWR*: $LWR(l_i) = \frac{\mathcal{L}(D|T_s^*, l_i)}{\sum_j \mathcal{L}(D|T_s^*, l_j)}$, where \mathcal{L} is the likelihood, D is the full alignment, and l_j are edges in T_s^* (Matsen et al., 2010).
- *insertion branch length*: Length of the best insertion branch of s in T_s^* , normalized by dividing by average branch length in T_s^* .
- *normalized distance to nearest node*: Distance of parent of s in T_s^+ to the closest node, normalized by dividing by average branch length in T_s^* .
- *pendant length*: Length of pendant branch incident to s in T_s^+ , normalized by dividing by average branch length in T_s^* .
- *insertion height*: Distance of parent of s in T_s^+ to the closest leaf that is not s , normalized by half the maximum distance of any two leaves in T_s^* .
- *#insertion locations*: Number of high-quality insertion locations for s as returned by epa-ng.
- *NJ TII*: Normalized TII of Neighbor Joining inference.
- *distance to low bootstrap edge*: Topological distance of insertion location to low bootstrap support (< 70) edge in T_s^* , normalized by the maximum distance of any internal edge to the insertion location.
- *dist diff insertion sibling*: Let C and C' be sister clades in T_s^* so that s is inserted on the edge connecting the root of C with the root of $C \cup C'$, and let a_s be the average pairwise sequence distance of s to C' and a_C the average pairwise sequence distance of C to C' . Then this summary statistic is $\frac{a_s}{a_C}$.
- *dist to insertion mean/SD*: Mean or standard deviation of topological distance between high-quality insertion locations as returned by epa-ng, normalized by dividing by the maximum distance of any two edges in T_s^* . 0 if there is only one best insertion location returned.
- *distance ratio mean/SD*: Mean or standard deviation of fraction of sequence distance (corrected by substitution model) to patristic distance (branch length distance) of all taxa t in to s in T_s^+ : $\frac{\text{seq_dist}(t,s)}{\text{patristic_dist}(t,s)}$.
- *ratio diff closest sequence mean/SD*: Mean and standard deviation of $\frac{\text{taxon_ratio}}{\text{closest_ratio}}$, which are the ratios of sequence distance to patristic distance as described above, for taxon s and the taxon that is closest to s in terms of sequence distance.
- *pythia difficulty*: Difficulty score computed with pythia (Haag et al., 2022) for the full alignments.

Figure S1: Pythia difficulty score for all 1,000 full alignments used in our analysis.

Figure S2: Classifier ROC curve for random forest predictions of normalized TII including bootstrap mean and standard deviation and Pythia difficulty as input features on the left and excluding them on the right.

Figure S3: Regression results for random forest predictions of TII excluding mean and standard deviation of bootstrap support values of inferred tree as features. Both plots display predicted vs actual normalized TII values but on the right, a \log_{10} scale is used.

Figure S4: Regression results for random forest predictions of disruption radius. Top row: results for random forests including mean and standard deviation of bootstrap values as features; bottom row: excluding these bootstrap features. Both columns display predicted vs actual disruption radius but on the right, a \log_{10} scale is used.

Figure S5: Feature importance of random forest predictions of disruption radius including mean and standard deviation of bootstrap values and Pythia difficulty as input features on the left and excluding them on the right. The higher its feature importance, the more influence a feature has on the final prediction. All feature importances sum up to one.

Figure S6: Classifier ROC curve for random forest predictions of significant instability (AU-test p-value < 0.05 and TII = 0) including bootstrap mean and standard deviation and Pythia difficulty as input features on the left and excluding them on the right.

Figure S7: Feature importance of random forest predictions of significant instability (AU-test p-value < 0.05 and TII = 0) including mean and standard deviation of bootstrap values and Pythia difficulty as input features on the left and excluding them on the right. The higher its feature importance, the more influence a feature has on the final prediction. All feature importances sum up to one.

29 **References**

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